

Operationalising An Integrated Holistic Impact Assessment To Accelerate Safe And Sustainable Design (SSbD) Acceptance In The Plastic Value Chain

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ABSTRACT

Plastic pollution is a major threat to humanity, requiring urgent action. Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), one of the most widely used plastics in long-life applications, poses significant environmental and health risks due to often containing plasticisers, such as phthalates, which can leach into the environment, causing potential harm to human health and ecosystems. Additionally, when burnt, PVC can release hazardous gases, including dioxins, which present acute and chronic health threats.

In this vein, the European ANALYST project aims to develop an integrated approach for a holistic health, environmental, social, and economic impact assessment that supports the transition towards safer and more sustainable industrial value chains (with a focus on the plastic sector) by influencing decision-making process and policymaking while also expanding the knowledge on the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD). To do this, the integrated approach will be tested through three use cases across the PVC value chain, namely suspension-PVC (flexible), emulsion-PVC (flexible) and suspension-PVC (foamed rigid). In all use cases, the conventional PVC will be compared with bio-circular attribution PVC, a material derived from renewable feedstocks, that aligns with circular economy principles.

The SSbD approach will be used to evaluate the impacts of conventional, more sustainable and safer alternatives to PVC. SSbD consists of five steps that perform hazardous assessment and sustainability assessment to address four dimensions: health, environmental, economic, and social.

This project includes three key components: (i) developing a comprehensive impact assessment methodology for plastics, including PVC, (ii) creating an open platform featuring a digital decision-making tool to facilitate better sustainability practices, and (iii) implementing a validation program for PVC applications in key sectors like automotive and construction.

To ensure the success of the validation program, a roadmap plan will be developed. Stakeholders will first receive comprehensive guidelines to test the innovative integrated approach. Through specialised training, they will evaluate traditional materials within the SSbD framework. Following this, stakeholders will identify specific requirements they aim to assess to drive innovation. The process will then involve gathering feedback and insights to perform a thorough analysis of lessons learned, existing gaps, and associated risks. This analysis will play a crucial role in improving the integrated approach and refining the SSbD framework while also offering actionable recommendations to ensure the framework's applicability extends beyond the project's lifespan. It is essential to highlight that this roadmap is iterative, requiring multiple revisions to shape the final vision effectively.

In the end, the ANALYST project represents a significant step forward in advancing an SSbD

approach for the innovation process for chemicals and materials across the PVC value chain and the broader plastic sector. By promoting sustainable industrial practices and healthier ecosystems, the project sets a foundation for a more resilient and sustainable future.

The ANALYST project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No 101138548.

Keywords: PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride); Bio-circular attributional PVC; Circular Economy; Sustainable decisions

Biography: Inês Costa holds a master's degree in Environmental Engineering from the University of Porto (Portugal). Currently, she is a Principal Researcher at PIEP – Centre for Innovation in Polymer Engineering, where she focuses on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Carbon Footprint studies, among other topics. Her work primarily revolves around evaluating the environmental, economic, and social impacts of materials and processes, with a special emphasis on the plastic sector. She aims to support the transition towards more sustainable practices and circular economy models by identifying and promoting solutions that can reduce the environmental footprint of industrial activities. She brings strong skills in teamwork, organisation, and a continuous drive for learning and innovation to all her projects. These capabilities allow her to collaborate effectively with cross-disciplinary teams, ensuring the successful execution of complex research tasks. In addition to her work as a researcher, she is also a certified trainer in environmental education and outreach, where she focuses on sharing her knowledge and expertise to guide others towards adopting more sustainable practices in their own industries and daily lives.